

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D7.12

Noise impacts on seabirds

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Author(s)	Manon Clairbaux (UCC), Mark Jessop (UCC)
Contributor	Paul Leahy (UCC)

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1	2024.04.27		William Leithead and James Carroll <i>William Leithead</i> <i>James Carroll</i>	<i>James Carroll</i>

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X-ROTOR Consortium

University of Strathclyde

Delft University of Technology

University College Cork – National University of Ireland, Cork

Fundacion Cener

General Electric Renovables España

Norwegian University of Science and Technology

CENER

NTNU - Trondheim
Norwegian University of
Science and Technology

UCC
Coláiste na hOllscoile Corcaigh, Éire
University College Cork, Ireland

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

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Description of the deliverable and its purpose

Displacement and collision have been clearly identified as an important concern for seabird populations in the context of offshore wind farm development. It is crucial to better understand the drivers of such risks to make informed decisions and appropriate mitigation. While numerous studies focussed on the impacts of underwater noise generated during installation and operation phases of offshore wind farms on marine wildlife, none have investigated the detectability of above-water turbine noise by seabirds and its potential impacts on collision and displacement risk.

In this report, we have reviewed and compared seabird hearing sensitivity to the predicted acoustic profile of the X-ROTOR turbine to draw conclusions regarding its detectability. While auditory 'warning' of turbine presence may reduce potential collision risk, we additionally discuss the potential for masking by turbine noise of biologically relevant signals, such as calls emitted at sea.

We determined that turbine auditory detectability depends on the seabird species considered and the position of the bird relative to the turbine. Preliminary results are limited to frequencies between 0.5 and 1 kHz and immediate surrounding of the turbine. Based on the available information on the noise profile of the X-ROTOR turbine design, we expect seabirds to detect the turbine by sight before they will be able to hear it. Sound propagation modelling is required to determine noise detectability from seabird colonies or important at-sea hotspot to rule out potential masking risk.

List of acronyms

DoA	Description of Action
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OREC	Ocean Renewable Energy Coalition
WESC	Wind Energy Science Conference
WP	Work Package
XRC	X-ROTOR concept

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Following the IPCC climate predictions (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2021) and in order to reach the Paris Agreement Objectives (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 2015), global greenhouse gas emissions must be reduced. Renewable energy has a fundamental part to play in global decarbonisation, and in 2018, targets of the European Union Renewable Energy Directive were revised upward, aiming for at least a 32% share of energy from renewable sources (European Parliament, 2018). In response, many countries are turning to wind energy, with short-term EU targets driving expansion of onshore/offshore wind farms. To ensure the lowest environmental cost per kW produced, effects of wind farms on ecosystems need to be carefully assessed (May et al., 2017).

Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) conducted during offshore wind farm pre-construction clearly identified interactions between turbines and marine wildlife, especially seabirds, as a concern (Bergström et al., 2014). Seabirds are among the most threatened of all bird groups globally (Dias et al., 2019), with effects of offshore wind farms including habitat loss due to barrier effect (Masden, Haydon, Fox, & Furness, 2010), displacement (Welcker & Nehls, 2016) and mortality by collision (Desholm, 2006), leading to population declines (Searle et al., 2014). Although numerous studies investigated the impacts of underwater noise generated by offshore wind farms on marine mammals, and in particular avoidance and displacement during the construction phase (Bailey et al., 2010; Madsen et al., 2006; Tougaard, 2021), little is known about how sound may be perceived by seabirds and how it could affect collision and disturbance risk.

Assessment of collision and displacement risks is often a requirement of consenting, and its over or underestimation could have profound effects on the sustainability of populations.

1.2 Marine megafauna use of acoustic cues

Understanding the propagation and perception of underwater noise is a key aspect of marine mammal ecology, with impacts associated with anthropogenic ocean noises being the topic of numerous studies (see for example Erbe et al., 2019; Madsen et al., 2006). In brief, marine mammals use sounds to communicate (Dudzinski, Thomas, & Gregg, 2009) as well as locate prey (Johnson et al., 2004) and oceanographic features (Tyack, 1997). They are able to hear over a wide bandwidth, much beyond what humans can detect (from 20 Hz to 20KHz). For example, whales perceive infrasounds (below 20 Hz) while dolphins can hear ultrasounds up to around 200 KHz. While our understanding of fish hearing is still limited (Popper et al., 2020), this topic has received increased attention over the last decade and has shown that many marine taxa are sensitive to sounds at low frequency including cephalopods, crustaceans and jellyfish (Radford, Tay, & Goeritz, 2022; Solé et al., 2016).

Diving seabirds also emit and react to underwater sounds (Hansen et al., 2017; Larsen, Wahlberg, & Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2020; McInnes et al., 2020; Sørensen et al., 2020) suggesting auditory system adaptation (Crowell et al., 2015) in particular for deep diving species such as penguins (up to 500m depth for some penguin species) and auks (up to 200 m depth for guillemots *Uria* spp.). Most seabird species are colonial, interacting with partner, chick and conspecifics using a variety of calls. Some studies have investigated seabird vocalisations during the breeding season (Dentressangle, Aubin, & Mathevon, 2012; Gémard, Aubin, & Bonadonna, 2019; Mulard et al., 2008), highlighting its roles in sexual selection or recognition of partners and/or chicks. However, little is known about the use of acoustic cues while at-sea, despite knowledge of

emitted calls in the context of foraging for several species (McInnes et al., 2020; Thiebault et al., 2019). Seabirds are certainly able to hear, but the perception of, and interaction with, their environment via hearing is still poorly understood. To better understand what kind of sounds seabirds might be able to perceive, studies are investigating the auditory sensitivity of seabirds (using electrophysiological or behavioural approaches (Mooney et al., 2019; Crowell et al., 2015). Further, the hearing of infrasound by seabirds has also been investigated (Patrick et al., 2021) as it can play a role in perception of oceanographic features or storms. Ultimately, an improved understanding of the acoustic cues used by seabirds will allow better mitigation measures for noisy anthropogenic infrastructures, including the potential use of sound repellents or attractors (Friesen, Beggs, & Gaskett, 2017).

1.3 Wind turbine noise impacts on wildlife

Terrestrial and marine ecosystems are becoming noisier with increasing anthropogenic development (Duarte et al., 2021; Erbe et al., 2019; Jerem & Mathews, 2021). This adds, potential stressors to wildlife through physiological damages, disturbance and/or masking signals of interest (Shannon et al., 2016). Wind farms are increasingly becoming part of the soundscape, producing mechanical (through vibrating components such as the gearbox) and aerodynamic (produced when the wind passes over turbine blades) noises (Van Treuren, 2018). Due to their potential effects on human communities, efforts have been made to identify and reduce wind turbine noise generation, characterize noise propagation to the surrounding environment and minimise effects of noise on communities (Hansen & Hansen, 2020). Regulations of wind turbine noises have been established worldwide, but threshold levels vary between countries (Teff-Seker et al., 2022).

Human responses to onshore wind farm noises have received considerable attention and demonstrated potential negative impacts (Knopper et al., 2014). However, few studies have focussed on the impacts on wildlife, but see published work on noise on livestock (Karwowska et al., 2015). Onshore wind turbine noise can increase stress levels (Agnew, Smith, & Fowkes, 2016) and modify behaviour (Whalen et al., 2018), and while it has been suggested that a human with normal hearing can probably hear a wind turbine blade twice as far away as can the average bird (Dooling, 2002), perception of wind turbine noise remains to be tested in many bird species.

Due to their remote locations, offshore wind turbines have received less attention when considering their noise, particularly as the ambient ocean noise is expected to be high, and the propagation of noise is particularly difficult to model at the water surface. To our knowledge, the only studies investigating offshore wind turbine noise has focussed exclusively on underwater noise. These studies have demonstrated that marine mammals and fish might avoid the ensonified area and/or experience hearing impairment (Thomsen et al., 2006), while some seabirds including terns and gulls didn't seem to be affected by underwater noise (Leopold & Camphuysen, 2007).

Although seabirds seem to rely heavily on sight when they are at-sea (see for example Darby et al., 2022; Thiebault et al., 2014), hearing sensitivity might enable them to detect wind turbines, particularly at night or during poor weather conditions when visibility is limited. More research is therefore needed to investigate potential impacts of above-water offshore wind turbine noise as it might affect attraction/disturbance of birds and therefore influence collision rates, avoidance of foraging grounds, or masking of biologically relevant signals.

1.4 Deliverable details

This report forms part of the Socio-environmental impact work package of the X-ROTOR project and aims to 1) assess the potential detectability and response to the X-ROTOR concept acoustic profile and consequent effects on collision, disturbance and masking risk and 2) summarize overall environmental impacts of the project. This report compares seabird acoustic sensitivity with the X-ROTOR turbine acoustic profile.

As no information is available on the underwater noise generated by the X-ROTOR turbine design during its life cycle, potential impacts on marine mammals, fish and other marine taxa cannot be covered by this report.

2 Methods

2.1 Review of seabird auditory sensitivity

To assess if seabirds will be able to detect the X-ROTOR turbine, we reviewed studies determining their auditory sensitivity in the air as well as underwater. To determine the seabird auditory sensitivity, wild or captive animals are usually submitted to stimulus of increasing intensity across different frequencies, with the minimal intensity that elicits a reaction considered as the threshold for the corresponding frequency. We considered both electrophysiological (measure of the auditory neural activity) and behavioural (recording of behavioural reactions) experiments even if some differences in results might occur (behavioural audiograms usually produce thresholds that are more sensitive (Crowell et al., 2015)).

2.2 Recording of auditory signals experienced by seabirds

The X-ROTOR turbine design could potentially mask biologically relevant signals at-sea such as conspecific calls. In order to identify such signals as well as describe the soundscape experienced by seabirds to assess masking risk, on-board microphones were deployed on three different seabird species (Manx Shearwater (*Puffinus puffinus*), Atlantic puffin (*Fratercula arctica*) and Northern gannet (*Morus bassanus*)). Acoustic recorders were also deployed at breeding colonies of Manx shearwater, Atlantic puffin and Lesser black-backed gull (*Larus fuscus*) to mitigate against lack of recordings on deployment birds. We randomly selected and analysed 10 calls per species (5 inside/5 outside burrows for Manx shearwaters). Deployment methods and recording parameters were previously described in Deliverable 7.11 and are summarised in Table 1. All recorded sounds were analysed and described with Audacity (version 3.1.3.0) and Raven Pro (version 1.6) software.

Masking is the process by which the threshold of hearing for one sound is raised by the presence of another one (masking sound) (American National Standard Institute, 2015). By definition, “a signal that is undetectable to a listener in quiet conditions cannot be masked. Similarly, a noise that is not detectable in quiet or ambient noise conditions can be ignored as a potential masker.” (Erbe et al., 2016). Determining if there are frequency overlaps between X-ROTOR noises and seabird signals recorded, we discussed the masking potential.

Table 1: Summary of microphone retrieval on the five seabird species studied

Species	Location	Dates	Models	Number of individual retrieved	Parameters
At colony					
Atlantic puffin	Skellig Michael & Little Saltee	07/2021 & 06/2021	Wildlife Acoustic Song Meter SM4	None	Sampling rate: 24 kHz Gain: 18 dB
Lesser black-backed gull	Little Saltee	07/2021			
Manx shearwater	Little Saltee	07/2021			
Inside burrow					
Manx shearwater	Little Saltee	07/2021 & 07/2022	Audiomoth & Audiomoth mini	10 & 17 nests	Sampling rate: 32 kHz Gain: Medium
On-board					
Atlantic puffin	Skellig Michael	10/07/21	Edic-Miny Weeny A110	1	Sampling rate: 16 kHz Gain: 24 dB
Manx shearwater	Little Saltee	07/2021	Edic-Miny Tiny B73	3	Sampling rate: 22 kHz Gain: unknown
Northern gannet	Great Saltee	07/2021	Edic-Miny Tiny B73	6	

2.3 Noise prediction of the X-ROTOR turbine

The X-ROTOR turbine consists of a primary rotor (vertical axis of the turbine), which has two upper and upper blades, and two secondary rotors (horizontal axis of the turbine), which are attached to the tips of the primary rotor's lower blades (see Figure 2).

Figure 1: The X-ROTOR concept and local reference frame coordinate systems (source: Deliverable 2.3)

The X-ROTOR aeroacoustic assessment has been conducted as part of Work Package 2 (see Deliverable M2.3 and D2.7). In brief, a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation was performed before using the outputs to predict the corresponding far-field sound pressure using the SIMULIA PowerACOUSTICS® and OptydB® software. The noise measurement simulation was conducted considering 15 microphones distributed at 200m from the turbine across vertical and horizontal planes with a sampling time of 22.5s and a supposed wind speed of 12.5m.s-1. All methods and parameters are described in the Deliverable M2.3 and D2.7.

The overall sound pressure level expressed in dB (pref= 2x 10-5 Pa) is presented in a cross-plane in Figure 3. The sound pressure level spectra (1 Hz bandwidth) produced by different components at different polar angles are illustrated in Figure 4. Sound pressure level spectra produced by the different blades are provided in D2.7.

Figure 2: Directivity pattern of the overall sound pressure level for, a) polar angles in x-z plane, and b) azimuthal angles in y-z plane (source: Deliverable 2.3)

The noise emitted from the primary rotor blades contributes the most to the total noise emitted. At all observer locations, the primary rotor blade noise dominates in low frequency region which maintains a constant level of about 90 dB and then declines rapidly. In comparison, the secondary rotors' noise contributes significantly above 400 Hz. The spectra also clearly show the directivity of the secondary rotor noise as the increase in the level of broadband noise at the upwind location $\theta_p=180^\circ$ is higher than that at other locations.

Figure 3: Comparison of sound pressure level spectra produced by different components of the X-ROTOR turbine at different polar angles. For a) $\theta_p=0^\circ$, b) $\theta_p=45^\circ$, c) $\theta_p=90^\circ$, and d) $\theta_p=180^\circ$ (source: Deliverable 2.3)

The turbine sound pressure spectra will be compared with seabird auditory sensitivity, their recorded emitted calls and the at-sea background noise (see above) to conclude on the detectability of the turbine by seabirds and to assess the risk of masking by the emitted noise.

3 Deliverable outcomes

3.1 Detectability of the X-ROTOR turbine noise by seabirds

Few studies have been conducted on seabirds (see Table 2), but they all demonstrated that they share a common region of peak sensitivity between 1 and 3 kHz (Hansen et al., 2020; Mooney et al., 2019; 2020; Crowell et al., 2015; 2016; Larsen et al., 2020; Maxwell et al., 2016; McGrew et al., 2022; Sørensen et al., 2020; Therrien, 2014).

Table 2: Review of seabird auditory peak sensitivity (source: McGrew et al., 2022)

Species	Medium	Method	Results	Authors
Common murre	In-air	Field based, AEP	Best sensitivity at 1–2 kHz	Mooney et al., 2019
	Underwater	Tank, behavioral observation	Reacted to underwater broadband bursts and mid-frequency sonar	Hansen et al., 2020
Atlantic puffin	In-air	Field based, AEP	Best sensitivity at 2.5 kHz	Mooney et al., 2019, 2020
Great cormorant	In-air	Tank, psychoacoustic	Best sensitivity at 2 kHz	Maxwell et al., 2016
		ABR	Best sensitivity at 1 kHz	Larsen et al., 2020
Gentoo penguin	Underwater	Tank, ABR	Best sensitivity at 1 kHz	Larsen et al., 2020
		Tank, behavioral observation	Graded reaction to noise bursts	Sørensen et al., 2020
Long-tailed duck	In-air	ABR	1–3 kHz	Crowell et al., 2016
		Underwater	Tank, psychoacoustic	Suggested sensitivity between 1.0 and 4.0 kHz
Lesser scaup	In-air	Tank, psychoacoustic	Best sensitivity at 2–3 kHz	Crowell et al., 2015
		ABR	1–3 kHz	Crowell et al., 2016
Northern gannet, red throated loon, black scoter, surf scoter, white-winged scoter, common eider, harlequin duck, ruddy duck	In-air	ABR	1–3 kHz	Crowell et al., 2016

AEP, auditory evoked potential; ABR, auditory brainstem response.

Comparing available audiograms (see for example Figure 4) from those studies with sound pressure level spectra of the X-ROTOR turbine, we concluded that the noise emitted at frequencies between 0.5 kHz and 1 kHz by the X-ROTOR turbine should be detectable by some species but not others. For those frequencies, the maximum sound pressure will be from 70 dB to 60 dB, for 0.5 kHz and 1 kHz respectively, when located 200 m away and upwind of the turbine. This is below the hearing sensitivity threshold of Northern gannet (see Figure 6) and Common guillemot (only one point available in-air at 1 kHz, (Mooney et al., 2019)) but above those described for Atlantic puffin (Mooney et al., 2020), Great cormorant (Larsen et al., 2020), and many diving ducks (Crowell et al., 2015), indicating that those species might be able to detect the turbine. However, the hearing threshold of many species for those frequencies is close to or above the sound pressure level (from 65 to 50 dB) when 200 m downwind of the turbine. The detectability of the X-ROTOR turbine might therefore vary with the location of the bird in relation to the turbine and wind direction.

Frequencies below 0.5 kHz haven't been tested during auditory sensitivity studies and we therefore can't conclude on the detectability of the X-ROTOR noise for those frequencies.

Figure 4: Average in-air audiograms from all species tested. Vertical bars represented +/- one standard deviation (source: Crowell et al., 2015).

3.2 *Masking*

For species such as Northern gannet the sound emitted by the X-ROTOR turbine won't be detectable (see above), so the risk of masking biologically relevant signals at-sea is extremely low.

Unfortunately, on-board microphone retrieved from Atlantic puffin and Manx shearwaters malfunctioned, precluding the description of their calls while at-sea. Nevertheless, the calls recorded at the colonies overlap with the range of frequencies emitted by the turbine (in particular for Atlantic puffin). However, the X-ROTOR is expected to be deployed far offshore (around 300km) limiting the likelihood that any generated noise will be perceived anywhere near colonies or even near coastal foraging locations limiting the risk of masking effects.

To fully assess at what distance noise could be detectable by seabirds at-sea and at the colony, and therefore risk to mask biologically relevant sound, sound propagation modelling is required. Further, additional on-board microphone deployments on species having lower hearing sensitivity (see above) will enable calls emitted at-sea and ambient noise to be more accurately determined in order to build a power spectrum model and conclude on at-sea potential masking.

4 **Conclusion and recommendations**

This study has demonstrated that the detectability of the X-ROTOR turbine noise is species-dependent. Species, such as the Atlantic puffin, are likely to detect it from a distance of 200m, while other species including Northern gannet, are unlikely to detect the turbine acoustically at a distance of 200m. Detectability at 200m also varies with the bird's location relative to the turbine, with sounds from an upwind direction being more detectable than those received downwind of the turbine.

At such distances, we anticipate that birds have likely already detected the turbine visually. For instance, Northern gannets have been observed visually detecting fishing boats up to 11km away (Bodey et al., 2014), limiting the role of auditory perception in collision avoidance. However, during night-time or poor visibility conditions, auditory perception of the turbine could assist birds in detecting and potentially reducing risk of collision. Conclusions regarding turbine detectability at greater distances and potential masking risks will necessitate further noise propagation modeling. Further, additional information about noises emitted at frequencies higher than 1kHz will enable a more comprehensive assessment of its detectability, considering that seabird auditory sensitivity peaks between 1 and 3 kHz. As the acoustic profile of the X-ROTOR turbines is expected to vary with factors such as wind speed and turbine maintenance (limiting noise due to biofouling vibrations), further measurements will be essential once the turbine is operational to draw conclusions on noise levels and potential detectability.

This study also underscores the lack of information on auditory sensitivity for numerous seabird species and the limitations of existing studies. Frequencies below 0.5 kHz are not commonly tested during auditory sensitivity assessments, and varying protocols can lead to different sensitivity thresholds (Crowell et al., 2015). Additionally, more studies recording calls and background noise are needed to identify biologically relevant signals for species of interest and better assess masking risks associated with anthropogenic activities. Free online repositories like Xeno-Canto (<https://xeno-canto.org>) could be valuable for studying calls and background noise inland, but on-board microphone deployments are necessary for studying at-sea acoustic seascapes and seabird repertoires.

To mitigate the impacts of noise generated by X-ROTOR technology on seabirds and marine mammals, as well as to reduce collision risks, we recommend the following actions:

1. Regularly review scientific studies assessing the hearing sensitivity of seabirds. Given the recent nature of this research field, many species lack relevant measurements. Up-date accordingly the detectability status of the X-ROTOR turbines.
2. Assess noises emitted at frequencies higher than 1kHz by X-ROTOR turbines to determine their detectability. Seabird auditory sensitivity peaks between 1 and 3 kHz, making this assessment crucial.
3. Conduct a noise propagation model to evaluate the future detectability of X-ROTOR wind farms by seabirds from colonies and key at-sea hotspots.
4. Quantify the risk of masking seabird calls and other relevant signals by the turbines, based on their detectability (refer to recommendation 3).
5. Develop visual and acoustic deterrents to mitigate seabird collisions with X-ROTOR turbines. Visual cues are likely to be perceived earlier than auditory ones, but acoustic deterrents may be effective during night-time or low visibility conditions. The acoustic deterrents must be detectable by relevant seabird species from a distance sufficient to allow avoidance of the turbines (refer to recommendation 3).
6. Quantify the underwater noise emitted during the construction, operation and dismantlement of the turbines without forgetting associated ship noises. Identify areas frequented by marine mammals throughout the year to minimize spatio-temporal overlap during construction, maintenance, and dismantlement phases. These activities can generate significant underwater noise levels, leading to adverse impacts on marine mammals.

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